

Studies on Mixed-Ligand Complexes of Copper. Part I. Copper-Malonate-Aminocarboxylate Complexes

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Formation and stability of mixed-ligand complexes of copper(II) with malonic acid as primary ligand and some amino acids as secondary ligands were determined by pH-metry and by polarography at 30° and at $\mu=0.25$ (KNO₃). $\Delta\log K$ and $\log X$ values indicate the favoured formation of mixed-ligand complexes with hetero donor atoms when compared to mixed-ligand complexes with identical donor atoms. The factors affecting the formation and stability of the mixed-ligand complexes are discussed.

MUCH attention has been paid to the studies of mixed-ligand complexes of metals in recent years because of their wide application in various fields of chemical activity and more particularly because of their presence in biological systems. In fact many naturally occurring metal complexes are mixed-ligand complexes¹. Such complexes are found to be of favoured formation and favoured stability. The factors influencing the formation of ternary complexes are many, of which the following three are important. (1) Ternary complexes containing multidentate ligands with different donor atoms (e.g., N and O) appear to be more stable than those with identical donor atoms (e.g., N and N or O and O). (2) The size of the chelate rings plays an important role. While in binary complexes of *3d* elements chelates with five-membered rings are more stable than chelates with six-membered rings for aliphatic ligands², in the case of mixed-ligand complexes, a chelate containing one five- and one six-membered ring turns out to be more stable than one containing either two five- or two six-membered rings³. (3) Steric effects also play a significant role in the formation and stability of mixed-ligand complexes.

In order to investigate the effect of these factors in the formation and stability of mixed-ligand complexes of Cu²⁺ involving ligands of biological importance, a study was undertaken of complexes formed by bidentate ligands containing hetero donor atoms. The studies presented in this paper involve the pH-metric investigations of the mixed-ligand complexes of Cu²⁺ with malonic acid as the primary ligand and some chosen amino acids as the secondary ligands.

Polarographic determination of the stability constants was undertaken since the reported applications of this technique are limited. Further it should serve as a good check on the results obtained by pH-titration.

Experimental

All reagents used were from standard manufacturers and of high purity. All the solutions were made in double distilled water and estimated by standard methods.

(a) *Measurements*: The titrations were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere in the solution at constant ionic strength, $\mu=0.25$ (KNO₃) in a thermostated bath at 30±0.1°. A digital pH meter (ECIL, pH 822A, accuracy ±0.01 pH unit) was used to measure the pH. The instrument was calibrated before each titration with 0.05M potassium hydrogen phthalate, pH 4.01 at 30°.

The polarograms were recorded with a recording polarograph (Radelkis OH 105 Universal Polarograph) with a three electrode set up. The electrode characteristics were: $h=40.0\pm 0.5$ cms, $t=3.85$ sec and $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}=4.23$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6}. The $E_{1/2}$ values were measured to an accuracy of ±0.5 mV and were reproducible to ±2 mV. The reversibility of each reduction was checked by measuring the difference in $E_{1/4} - E_{3/4}$ values.

(b) *Ionisation constants of the ligands*: The ionisation constants of malonic acid, glycine, α -alanine, serine and β -alanine were determined under laboratory conditions used in this work by the method of Albert and Sergeant⁴ and found to agree well with the values reported in the literature. The values are given in Table 1 along with binary stability constants.

(c) *Stability constants*: The determination of the stability constants of 1:1 and 1:2 binary complexes were carried out by the method of Chaberek and Martell⁵.

TABLE 1—IONISATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COPPER BINARY COMPLEXES. $\mu=0.25$ (KNO₃) AT 80°

Ligand	pK ₁	pK ₂	log K ₁	log β ₂
1. Malonic Acid	2.62	5.22	5.10	7.65
2. Glycine	2.32	9.66	8.26	15.17
3. α-Alanine	2.58	9.58	8.20	14.90
4. Serine	2.17	8.81	7.56	14.01
5. β-Alanine	8.54	10.20	7.10	12.69

The formation of the mixed-ligand complexes were studied under the same conditions as for binary complexes, except that the solutions contained equivalent amounts of malonic acid and amino acid. In addition, titrations with the same concentration of the metal ion and the two ligands in excess (upto 3 times) were also carried out in order to try the possibility of the formation of higher complexes.

Complex formation in systems such as those under study is the result of a competition between metal ions and protons (Lewis acids) with the ligand (Lewis base). Under low pH conditions, because of the protonation of the ligands, the extent of metal-complex formation is not high. With higher pH, hydroxyl ions compete with the ligand base for the metal so that hydroxo complexes are present in appreciable concentration. The nature of the species present in the solution is therefore highly pH-dependent. In the present study of copper-malonate-aminocarboxylate system, the pH range 3-8 has been chosen so that protonated and hydroxyl species are kept at a minimum.

The following species were taken into account in the computation of the stability constant of the mixed-ligand complexes :

H₂A, HA, A, H₂B, HB, B, CuA, CuA₂, CuB, CuB₂, CuAB and Cu, where H₂A=malonic acid and H₂B=protonated amino acid. Charges are not included for convenience.

The method of calculation used is a modification of that of Nasanen and Koskinen^{6,7}. A computer programme was developed to calculate the stability constant of the mixed-ligand complex and the concentrations of all the species mentioned above.

The method of DeFord and Hume⁸ for determining consecutive overall stability constants of binary complexes as extended by Schaap and McMasters⁹ was used for the computation of stability values from polarographic measurements.

Results and Discussion

The extent to which a mixed-ligand complex is favoured in formation is expressed in terms of

$\Delta \log K$ and $\log X$ which have the significance explained below. The equilibria involved in the formation of a mixed-ligand complex and the relevant equilibrium constants are :

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{\text{CuAB}} - \log K_{\text{CuB}} \quad \dots (3)$$

Normally, the value of $\Delta \log K$ must be negative because $K_{\text{CuB}} > K_{\text{CuB}_2}$, there being more coordination positions available when CuB is formed than when CuB₂ is formed from CuB. From statistical considerations, the most appropriate value for $\Delta \log K$ has been estimated to be -0.9 for a distorted octahedral complex of Cu²⁺ with two bidentate ligands⁸. Hence an experimentally determined value of $\Delta \log K = -0.9$ or more indicates favoured formation of the mixed-ligand complex.

Under pH-metric conditions, the ligand is not present in a concentration very much in excess of that of the Cu²⁺. Therefore, the concentration of 1 : 1 binary complexes will be appreciable throughout. Hence this $\Delta \log K$ approach involving the constants of 1 : 1 complexes, is best suited for each studies.

In the polarographic method, the ligand must necessarily be present in very large excess to that of the metal ion so that the highest binary and mixed-ligand complexes will always be present. So the $\Delta \log K$ formalism is not applicable here. Another way of expressing the stability of the mixed-ligand complexes is to calculate the equilibrium constant of the "disproportionation" reaction

$$X = \frac{[\text{CuAB}]^2}{[\text{CuA}_2][\text{CuB}_2]} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{and, } \log X = 2 \log \beta_{\text{CuAB}} - (\log \beta_{\text{CuA}_2} + \log \beta_{\text{CuB}_2}) \quad \dots (6)$$

This log X approach has a firm statistical foundation. The value expected for X on statistical reasoning is 4, i.e., $\log X = 0.6^{10-12}$. Under purely statistical conditions it is expected that the mixed-ligand complex is present to the extent of 50% and the binary complexes to the extent of 25% each. Here too an observed value of $\log X = 0.6$ or more indicates favoured formation of the mixed-ligand complex.

Results of studies on mixed-ligand complexes formed by copper-malonate with selected amino acids by pH-metric and polarographic techniques

are presented in Table 2. The values obtained by these two methods are in good agreement. Titrations with higher ratios of ligands to Cu^{2+} showed no indication of the formation of species other than the 1 : 1 : 1 complex.

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF MIXED-LIGAND COMPLEXES OF THE FORMULA $\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{L})$. $\mu = 0.25(\text{KNO}_3)$ AT 30°

L	pH-metry		Polarography	
	$\log \beta_{\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{L})}$	$\Delta \log K$	$\log \beta_{\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{L})}$	$\log X$
1. Glycinate	12.93 ± 0.05	-1.03	12.40 ± 0.05	1.98
2. α -Alaninate	12.08 ± 0.08	-1.22	12.02 ± 0.04	1.49
3. Serinate	11.41 ± 0.05	-1.25	11.51 ± 0.05	1.86
4. β -Alaninate	10.95 ± 0.06	-1.25	10.99 ± 0.04	1.64

The pH dependence of the half-wave potential often provides useful information regarding the electrode reactions, and the nature of the different species present in different pH regions. Because of their basic nature, the ligands are associated with protons over a wide range of pH. These protons which get replaced by metal ions on complexation, recombine with the ligand liberated when the complex is reduced under polarographic conditions. The protonation will however be dependent on the deprotonation constant (pK) of the coordinating group and the solution pH. If the pH of the solution is less than the pK of a particular coordinating group of the ligand, the ligand liberated from the electrode surface on reduction of the complex will combine with protons from the solution in order to come to equilibrium with it. If the $E_{1/2}$ is measured as a function of pH, a plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH gives valuable information regarding such ligand-proton interactions at the surface.

In the present study on the mixed-ligand complexes in copper-malonate-aminocarboxylate systems, a plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH in the pH range of 6-7 yielded a straight line showing that only a single species was present. The slope of the straight line was ~ 0.030 corresponding to one proton. This would protonate the $-\text{NH}_2$ group of the amino acid, considering the lower pK values of the carboxyl groups.

Lingane^{1,2} has derived the following equation, relating the $E_{1/2}$ of the complex with 'p', the number of ligands bound to the metal.

$$\frac{d(E_{1/2})}{d \log [L^-]} = p \frac{0.0591}{n} \text{ at } 25^\circ \quad \dots (7)$$

A plot of $E_{1/2}$ of the complex vs $-\log [L^-]$ should give a straight line with a slope of $p \frac{(0.0591)}{n}$ from which the number of coordinated ligands, 'p' may be obtained. In the case of Cu^{2+} complexes, the reduction of the metal ion at the electrode occurs in a single stage, n should be 2 and the slope of the straight line should be $p(0.0296)$.

Such determinations were applied with modifications to the ternary systems in this work. Keeping the pH and the concentration of the primary ligand (malonate) constant, the concentration of the secondary ligand (aminocarboxylate) was varied. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log [\text{aminocarboxylate}]$ yielded a straight line with a slope ~ 0.030 , and hence the value of $p=1$, showing that only one aminocarboxylate was coordinated to the 1 : 1 copper-malonate complex.

Table 3 presents values of $\Delta \log K$ and $\log X$ for some mixed-ligand complexes of copper, including those in Table 2 for comparison.

As already pointed out, three factors appear as significant in determining the relative stabilities of the mixed-ligand complexes viz., nature of the donor atoms, steric effects and ring sizes.

The mixed-ligand complexes examined in the present work contain two bidentate groups, a dicarboxylate and an aminocarboxylate involving totally three oxygens and one nitrogen as donor atoms. The dicarboxylate chosen viz., malonate which forms a six membered chelate was kept constant and the aminocarboxylate yielding a five/six membered ring was varied. The stoichiometry is 1 : 1 : 1 (copper : malonate : aminocarboxylate) in all the chelates under study. Table 2 shows the

TABLE 3—Log β , $\Delta \log K$, AND $\log X$ VALUES OF SOME COPPER MIXED CHELATES

Sl. No.	Mixed chelate	$\log \beta$	$\Delta \log K$	$\log X$	μ	Temp. $^\circ\text{C}$	Ref.
1.	$\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{ox})$	7.99	-1.58	0.92	1.5	28	21
2.	$\text{Cu}(\text{ssa})(\text{gly})$	16.04	-1.20	1.02	1.0	25	19
3.	$\text{Cu}(\text{sal})(\text{ser})$	16.55	-1.14	0.89	0.15	37	20
4.	$\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{gly})$	12.83	-1.05	1.98	0.25	30	This work
5.	$\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{ala})$	12.08	-1.22	1.49	0.25	30	This work
6.	$\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{ser})$	11.41	-1.25	1.86	0.25	30	This work
7.	$\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{bala})$	10.95	-1.25	1.64	0.25	30	This work
8.	$\text{Cu}(\text{ox})(\text{en})$	14.49	-0.79	0.94	0.1	25	22
9.	$\text{Cu}(\text{ox})(\text{pn})$	14.31	-0.55	3.14	0.1	25	22
10.	$\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{en})$	14.78	-0.76	2.81	0.1	25	22
11.	$\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{pn})$	13.62	-1.30	2.55	0.1	25	22
12.	$\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{en})$	17.15	-1.30	1.10	0.1	25	28

Abbreviations : ala = α -alaninate, bala = β -alaninate, bipy = 2,2'-bipyridyl, en = ethylenediamine, gly = glycinate, mal = malonate, ox = oxalate, pn = 1,3-propylenediamine, sal = salicylate, ssa = 5-sulfosalicylate and ser = serinate.

Following order of overall stability, $[\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{gly})] > [\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{ala})] > [\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{ser})]$. Though serine contains a third function in its hydroxyl group, this group is known to be involved in coordination only above $\text{pH } 10^{14}$. Since the present studies are restricted to the biologically important pH range 3-8, coordination by hydroxyl group is not considered. The observed decrease in stability, glycinate > alaninate > serinate is attributed to steric factors. This conclusion is confirmed by the values of $\Delta \log K$ and $\log X$ in the case of these systems.

In the case of the β -alaninate, comparison with α -amino acids is not strictly valid because of the difference in ring size. The general conclusion is that a mixed-ligand complex containing one five- and one six-membered ring has preferred stability over those with either two five-membered or two six-membered rings⁴. This conclusion is borne out by the data in Table 3. $[\text{Cu}(\text{ox})(\text{pn})]$ has more positive value of $\Delta \log K$ than $[\text{Cu}(\text{ox})(\text{en})]$. The same conclusion is valid in comparing the value for $[\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{gly})]$ with that for $[\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{bala})]$, the latter being the less preferred one. It would be instructive to have values for $[\text{Cu}(\text{ox})(\text{gly})]$ and similar systems. Investigation of such systems is rendered very difficult due to formation of precipitate of $[\text{Cu}(\text{ox})]$ even at low pH values^{1,5-18}.

The $\Delta \log K$ and $\log X$ values for mixed-ligand complexes of copper with bidentate ligands containing only nitrogen or only oxygen as donor atoms and also mixed-ligand complexes with both nitrogen and oxygen donors are presented in Table 3. It is seen that the mixed-ligand complexes of copper reported in this work involving three oxygen atoms and one nitrogen atom as donors, have $\Delta \log K$ and $\log X$ values intermediate between those of the mixed-ligand complexes containing only nitrogen or only oxygen donors and those with two nitrogen atoms and two oxygen atoms as donors. This clearly indicates the favoured formation of these mixed-ligand complexes to those containing identical donor atoms.

The distribution of various species present in a particular system as a % of the total copper concentration and their variation with the pH of the solution gives a good idea of the favoured formation of mixed-ligand complexes as also pH effects. As a representative system, $[\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{gly})]$ is presented in Fig. 1. Here the concentration of $[\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{gly})]$ reaches a maximum of 46% of total copper at $\text{pH } 6.32$. At low pH , $[\text{Cu}(\text{mal})]$ complex is the major species present. As pH increases the concentration of $[\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2]$ species starts rising. This is expected from the ionisation constants of the two ligands. For the other three systems studied, namely, $[\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{ala})]$, $[\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{ser})]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{bala})]$, the maximum concentrations of mixed chelates are 32% at $\text{pH } 6.24$, 28% at 5.86 and 30% at $\text{pH } 7.26$

Fig. 1. The distribution of various species as a function of pH . Curve 1. Cu^{2+} , 2. $[\text{Cu}(\text{mal})]$, 3. $[\text{Cu}(\text{mal})(\text{gly})]$, 4. $[\text{Cu}(\text{gly})]$ and 5. $[\text{Cu}(\text{gly})_2]$.

respectively. The extent to which the mixed-ligand complexes formed depends not only on the relative and absolute concentrations of the metal ion and ligands that are present, but also on the relevant pK and stability constant values as well as on the pH of the solution.

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